

Geological Investigation of the Area around thermal Springs of the Uvira geothermal Fields,

DRC, Southern the WBEARS

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ABSTRACT

Keywords:

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In the eastern Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) lies the West Branch of the EARS. This depression contains numerous geothermal reservoirs that are shared with neighboring nations. Surface thermal manifestations can be found in two distinct lithologies in the eastern Democratic Republic of Congo: the youngest (Cenozoic) along the rift axes and the cratonic (Proterozoic) above the rift. This study advances our understanding of the rocks surrounding the thermal springs at Uvira, on the south shore of Kivu Lake in the province of South Kivu, through geological updates. The grabens between Kivu and Tanganyika Lakes contain roughly many thermal springs: Nyangezi, Kanvivira, Kichulo, Ubwari, Runingu, ... Geological and tectonic analyses have all focused on diaclasses, which are fissured outcrops, faults, and joints. Our study found that the rocks surrounding Kanvivira thermal spring are magmatic rocks (Granit), while Runingu thermal spring is characterized by metamorphic rock such as quartzite, and Pemba thermal spring is also metamorphic rock. Facies are composed of crystalline schists, gabbroic Amphibolites, Amphibolo-schists with colorless Amphiboles, garnet micaschists, quartzites, and biotite gneisses, while plutonic rocks are primarily granitic and syenitic rocks. The Kivu rift has been identified as seismically active since the first half of the twentieth century. The rifts in Uvira are NE-SW oriented. The rocks around Kanvivira have a preferred direction of N300 with a dip of 50, while Runingu has a dip trending westward. Lithoclasses (joints, diaclasses) have a direction of N 155 and a dip of 40, Kanvivira's deformation range is faults, while Runingu's range is joints; veins are uncommon and typically stockworks. Some other hot springs are located at Lemera on the high plateau.

1. INTRODUCTION

The western branch of the East African Rift system is cut into uplifted structures in the Precambrian basement (Matsuzawa 1969). It is bounded by a series of normal faults, which are mostly Tertiary in age but have been rejuvenated in the Quaternary. These faults are characterized by repeated westward end echelon offsets towards the south. The rift floor is occupied by a few large, deep lakes, of which Lake Kivu has the highest elevation, almost 1500m above sea level (H-K Wong and R. P. Von Herzen 1973). The block between the lakes Kivu and Tanganyika (Figure 1) is a Chenal resulted of the African rifting and is full of sedimentation events. This basin is surrounded by cratons aged Precambrian in terms of horst and or rift bulb after tectonic fracturation of the central African. The unique river within this rift segment is the Ruzizi which discharge of the northern Lake Kivu supplying the Lake Tanganyika in the south. All lakes are generated by rift activity, and the valley and borders are lightly checked by tectonism in the form of seismicity. Thus, the reactivation of the intercrust by magmatism or dyke is a probable case. The presence of heat flux within this thin part of the region is not negligible and is attested to by some geothermal manifestations located on all sides of the Ruzizi River

serving as rift axes in this area. This means that in Rwanda, Burundi is on the east side, oppositely to the DRC on the west flank. Except for Bukavu, each city in the Ruzizi basin has a thermal spring that differs in chemical characteristics, maybe due to the geological basements or geotechnical behavior of each one.

Some thermal resurgences are directly directly at young formations, while others are carried out on deformed fields. The city of Uvira in the DRC, on the north shoreline of the Tanganyika Lake, is located between two geothermal fields, Runingu in the north and Pemba in the south. The nearest and most accessible thermal spring of all is Kamvirira, which is around 5km from the city. It has some small pools in the Uvira territory of south Kivu province. The city of Uvira in the Southern Hemisphere is on the north-western shore of Lake Tanganyika, between latitude 3°21'S and longitude 29°12'E. The region of Uvira is the southern extension of the Ruzizi Plain. Structurally, the Ruzizi plain is part of the African rift system, more specifically the Western Rift, which is thought to have been formed during the Eocene. (H. BELLON et A. POUCKET, 1980). The aim of the study was to sample all different lithologies and physical superficial parameters in the focused area. The methodological approach integrates the geological information acquired.

Figure 1. Location of the study area between Lakes Kivu and Tanganyika.

1.1 Geological Features

The tectonic evolution of the Kivu rift is witnessed by the Lake Kivu structural and sedimentological features (Pouclet et al., 2016) in the south of the Nyiragongo and the seismicity of the surroundings of the Tanganyika lake on the southern sides. Volcanism of the South-Kivu province, centred on Kahuzi Biega with outcrops at Kamanyola is carried by a crossing of the NW-SE and NNE-SSW fault sets (Ebinger et al., 1999).

The Ruzizi plain is the northern extension of Lake Tanganyika, descending 373 meters from the lake's present level at 773 meters to Lake Kivu. According to Ilunga, the Precambrian (basement) and Cenozoic (secondary cover) units represent its geology. Older topography emerges on fault escarpments enclosing the plain or on mini-horsts dividing the plain into smaller basins. The names for it are Burundian and Ruzizian, in that order, from bottom to top. The cover units are thick (8 to 10,000 m) and have a pelitic-arenaceous character. The mini-horsts and basics (dolerites, microgabbros, and gabbros) that are more noticeable at lower altitudes astride the Ruzizi are augmented by acid magmatic intercalations (granites, pegmatites). They are primarily composed of schists,

quartzophyllades, quartzites, micaschists, gneisses, migmatites, dolomitic limestones, and mylonites, and are more metamorphosed at their base (Ruzizian) than at their top (Burundian) (Ilunga, n.d.). The essential sand, sandstone, conglomerate, and the uncommon but easily identifiable argillites found along the terraces make up the geothermally less significant Cenozoic assemblage.

On the Kiliba-Uvira axis, on the western edge of the northern end of Lake Tanganyika, rocks of Paleoproterozoic age are exposed, consisting largely of gneisses, quartzites and micaschists belonging to the Rusizian basement. Layers of varying thickness alternate between quartzites and micaschists on the other side of the town of Uvira, parallel to Lake Tanganyika. Amphibolites, gneisses, and pegmatites are dotted with veins of white quartz that are generated from fissures. Structurally, the working zone displays two fault types visible on the western rim of Lake Tanganyika: an N-S fault directly dominates the lake. Gloire Bamulezi (2020) showed this as responsible of the Kavimvira hydrothermal activity.

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

The aim of the study was to sample all different lithologies in the focused area in the different compartments of the fault zones, i.e., from the fresh sample to the more and more fractured and weathered zones in the damaged zone to the completely weathered rocks in the fault core or meteoric-weathered horizons. On these samples, different petrophysical measurements, including thin-section observations, have been performed to characterize the

evolution of the reservoir properties of the different lithologies. The pH is also influenced by the fluid's salinity, temperature, and temperature and by mineral buffers. Electrical conductivity and pH were measured using standardised methods; in-situ temperature measurement was carried out using the integrated temperature sensor of the meter's electrodes and a calibrated glass thermometer (Ewa Kmiecik et al.).

Figure 2: Homogeneous cross-border synthetic geological map of the study region (background) with overprinted neotectonic features (neotectonic faults, late Quaternary volcanic centers, thermal springs, and fossil hydrothermal travertine).

the methodology adopted for this work was based mainly on documentation, and the results obtained were validated by a fieldwork control.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Uvira (Kanvinvira) Thermal Spring

As mentioned above, this thermal manifestation is easily accessible as it is located on the national road not far from the city. Its physico-chemical parameters are appreciable among others in the region. With a pH of 6.9, it's probably a pathway whose source is lightly neutered. This is the hottest of the Congolese Ruzizi sides, with a temperature of 66.5 °C. Unfortunately, its measured conductivity range of 1493 μ S is not the

biggest, but it gives us quick information about the possibility of dissolved ions in the hot water and the capacity of conducting electric power into the steam. The water is clear with no sulfide or oxide traces; however, life traces are attested by some white algae (fig 3D). Outcrops are essentially acids.

Granitoids (fig.3C) are made of white minerals, quartz and feldspar-sized grains accompanied by visible micas. The extension (fig.3A) This unity makes the surroundings of this at a direct foot of escarpments and is associated with Tinous granitoids of the Mitumba. Blocs of rich silica (Fig.3B) Considered, phyllades are not roots in the near space. This thermal manifestation lies in the contact of Precambrian and Cenozoic fields with the assistance of felsic intrusion and witnesses a tectonic control demonstrated by the map in Figure 3.

Figure. 3 Some lithologies around Kanvinvira thermal spring are: A) an outcrop of acid rocks, B) blocks of quartzophyllades within the pool; C) a pegmatite boulder; and D) an alga colony around the window of the thermal venue.

3.2 Runingu thermal spring

The spring is located between the National Road and Ruzizi River at about 3km NE of the National Road, being accessible in the plain. The greenish-gray coloration on its surface which already testifies to the life within, the associated pool appears as a surface of 5m² used for washing up and bathing (Fig.4). Considering its temperature of 36.6°C, it is the coldest of the group, but the bubbling still indicates the presence of some escaping gases. It is simply worthwhile to integrate the electrical conductivity, which is 800 μ S and regarded as average, with its lithology and/or roots in conductive isons. The bedrock is quartzite that has been modified by desiccation to include some iron oxides in microcracks. The hydrogen potential pH, which is 8.98 and hence basic, exhibits a small imbalance with respect to the surface-visible formations, indicating a varied lithological column that ranges from basic to acidic. Furthermore, according to Keith Nicholson (1993), this result is the proof of one of the micro horsts in this savannah plain. A geothermal fluid may boil as it rises to the surface because of the drop in hydrostatic pressure; cooling may be possible at high

flow rates. A fluid may have enough time to lose heat through conduction to the cooler host rocks if it rises to the surface slowly.

3.3 Pemba Thermal Spring

Thirty Kilometers south of Uvira, you'll find this spring. The recovery is observable over an approximate 20-meter² area, just a short distance from Lake Tanganyika's edge. Because of this approximation, it is susceptible to lacustrine transgression. Now, lacustrine waters cover it, and the only indication of its existence is the boltings across the schistosity planes. Furthermore, the whole extent of its extension is below the national road, which has been abandoned because of Lake Overflow and invasion by Lake Tanganyika's waters (Fig.5). With a 673 μ S electrical conductivity, it is less than that of Runingu, Kamvivira, and even the lithology of Pemba is based on schists. The lithology along the NE-SW schist in Pandage. The water's non-evaluable color changes when it meets the rocks, and this directly affects the temperature, which was 40.2°C. Gass's wealth indicates its internal strength, and its pH is estimated to be 6.85.

Figure 4: (A) Runingu thermal pool, (B) Pegmatite outcrop; (C) autochthone alteration upon acid rocks, (D) Quartzite benches.

Figure 5. Thermal pool on the roadbed A), view of the amplacement of the spring on the banks of the Tanganyika B), schistose rocks around the pool C), breccia and tropézienne breccia with bubbling D).

4. DISCUSSION

The first step in evaluating a geothermal resource is to review and analyze all surficial data (geochemical, hydrological, lithological, geophysical, etc.) that may or may not be available for the area. According to [IGA Service GmbH \(2013\)](#), surveys may be used in many situations. Because it correlates with the total solid dissolved rate of a sample, the measurement of electrical conductivity (EC) is crucial to water studies ([Witczak et al., 2013](#)). Furthermore, the pH can be affected by the liquid's salinity, temperature, and mineral content ([Keith Nicholson, 1993](#)). As explained by [Fournier \(1985\)](#), the reactions between quartz and wairakite-Ca-montmorillonite illustrate this phenomenon.

4.1 Lithology

The central African interlacustrine region, which borders the western branch of the East African Rift and is primarily found near the Kivu and Edouard lakes (formerly Edouard), is currently home to a few known alkaline and hyperalkaline complexes ([Lubala et al., n.d.](#)). These complexes range in latitude from 1° to 3° south. The eastern Tanzanian region, encompassing the Biega Mountain near Bukavu City, is home to an annular pluto-volcanic complex that intrudes into the Kibaro-burundian metasediments. The Ruzizi geothermal fields are situated between Kaynzu in Burundi and the Biega and Miki Alkaline complexes in Congo. Results showed a North-South polarity that influenced the lithosphere's distension's axial propagation. It is situated along the East African Rift's western branch. Significant subsidence is a feature of the Tanganyika basin, but the primary cause is volcanic activity ([Kampunzu et al., 1998](#)). The information that is currently available permits the possibility that there are magmatic bodies located in

the crust or at the base. There are some magmatic rocks in this triangle group. Completely unreported fundamental incursions are mentioned in Kamanyola, and Doleritic cells are encountered near Burundian Ruzizi springs.

The lithostratigraphy of Uvira is characterised by two lithological assemblages, represented by Precambrian metamorphic rocks of the Kibaran age and recent Cenozoic rocks of the Tanganyika rift age. Several other NNE-SSW-trending fractures affecting relatively weathered gneisses have been observed on the hills overlooking the town of Uvira. The Uvira thermal hydrothermal springs are aligned along the same NNE-SSW direction (Runingu, Kanvinvira, Pemba). Figure 6 below shows the healthy samples of rocks from the various thermal springs. Figure A shows a rock with a greyish texture and a whitish color, dominated by silica (quartz), followed by feldspars and micas. The rock is thought to be granite, while figure B shows a rock essentially composed of quartz and is thought to be quartzite, and C is schistose rock from Pemba Spring. As both pH and total ion concentration are important factors in predicting fluid behavior in subsurface reservoirs and surface operations involving natural waters, it becomes necessary to model the solution with respect to these variables. Moreover, for minerals that dissolve at a low pH, the total dissolved solids (TDS) in the solution will increase. The concentration (TDS) can still change at constant temperature and pH due to the water-rock ratios).

4.2 Tectonics and deformations

The entire region was subsequently deformed during the Rodinia amalgamation, at about 1000 Ma ago, and anorogenic alkaline complexes were emplaced at ~750 Ma ([Delvaux et al., 2017](#)).

Figure 6: Formations found around the Uvira thermal sites

Fissural eruption of continental nephelinites north of Idjwi Island marked the beginning of rifting in the North Tanganyika Kivu region during the mid-Miocene (20–21 Ma).

The compressive movement has a NE-SW orientation. This is the area affected by volcanism, whose activity continues (hot springs in several places). A plutonism marked by the presence of acid rocks whose exhumation was made possible by erosion is remarkable (Birindwa & Mwesige, 2020) and geothermal springs and hydrothermal travertine occurring on a specific line defining faults and fracture networks have long been recognized as features of the Kivu rift region (Boutakoff, 1933; Passau, 1933; Deelstra et al., 1972; Delvaux et al., 2017). The rift domain is unquestionably a sequence of typical faults that followed an extension brought about by forces acting on the Tanzanian and Congolian cratons. These three thermal springs are

connected to a continuous fault that runs along the west escarpment of Lake Tanganyika, as seen on the map in Figure 9. Indeed, as on Burundi's opposite side, earthquakes can cause resurgences to migrate or disappear, affecting the hydrothermal regime there. The best materials to withstand the shocks caused by tectonic events are rocks. According to Sivihwe (2019), Certain joints and diaclases have been observed in the vicinity of thermal springs. Pegmatite materials are used to fill large fractures in specific cases (fig. 7). Before arriving at Pemba Spring in the southern part of Uvira, coastal escarpments display a new schist series that is gray, green, and black with a high degree of microdeformation (Fig. 7A). The main fault regulating hydrothermal activity is an N-S, and the Ruzizian plain is home to young faults that are responsible for thermal springs in and around the rift axis by Tanganyika Lake (fig. 2).

Figure 7. View of open fractures: joints and diaclases in the sector

Figure 8: The stereograms show the results of stress inversion using the Win-Tensor program, based on the mechanisms corresponding to the two seismotectonic zones equivalent to the study area.

Proven by Gloire G et al., to the south, in the Uvira territory, the normal faults described at Kavimvira ($R' = 0.44$; Shmin : $\text{N}127^\circ\text{E}$) and at Kalundu ($R' = 0.53$; Shmin : $\text{N}95^\circ\text{E}$) are associated. The Kavimvira faults are offset in direction. This shift can be explained by the fact that these are reactivation faults that have preserved the direction of pre-existing fractures belonging to an earlier tectonic phase. According to Shungu L. (2018), the structural analysis of the conjugate fractures encountered shows that these fractures are derived slightly from extension and greatly from compression resulting from stresses σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_3 , whose dip/azimuth values (in degrees) are shown in the figure above, σ_1 : $\text{N}14^\circ\text{E}/6^\circ\text{NNE}$, σ_2 :

$\text{N}99^\circ\text{E}/41^\circ\text{WNW}$ and σ_3 : $\text{N}112^\circ\text{E}/49^\circ\text{ESE}$. These conjugate fractures show the alternation of an extension following posterior rifting and a compression, whose general folding in this region is observed on a large scale. This is thought to underlie the deformations observed in the field, which are likely to be the markers of dislocations and microfaults. The different directions of the joints, drop-offs, diaclasses and veins attest to the existence of two phases of local deformation. The first phase produced syntectonic breaks in the first Kibaran regional folding, while the second phase produced breaks that accompanied the shearing of the East African rifting into the Tanganyikian trend.

Figure 9. This map shows the thermal springs of the Kivu and Tanganyika rifts and fault tectonic settings within the DRC and Burundi. Circled in a black rectangle is the study area. Thermal activity in Grabens beyond the Mitumba mountain chain

Two basins, the Ruzizi to the east and the Itombwe to the west, are prominently displayed on the large-scale map of the region found in figure 11. Both contain sediments or metasediments and are adjacent to the Mitumba, a mega horst that is bound by faults. Thermal springs are evidence of the heat beneath the Mitumba mountain range and are found along these faults. The Walikale group to the west and the Virunga group to the east are both in the same location at the center of the branch; the only distinction is that the latter is active volcanically.

4.2 Mineralogy

Confirmation of the nature of the limestone rocks was obtained following tests carried out in the field using hydrochloric acid (HCl); effervescence was observed on these rocks after the application of the acid, where effervescence corresponds to the release of CO_2 . For

most of the altered rocks the oxides and hydroxides as well as certain deposits of sulfide, and the sludges from hydrothermal alteration assimilated to clays.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the geological investigation of springs in Uvira region aimed at the geolocalization of thermal potential in that area, and a pedestrian survey was applied, taking measurements of petrophysical aspects such as electrical conductivity, hydrogen potential, and in-situ temperature measurement. This approach to the Uvira geothermal springs was based on: Reconnaissance Study: The reconnaissance study is usually carried out on a regional scale to identify potential targets for further, more-detailed geothermal exploration.

A good outcome of the geological analysis is a clear picture of the regional and local geology, stratigraphy,

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and tectonic structure of the area, as well as the identification of uncertainties and data gaps that need to be addressed in subsequent stages of exploration. This information should indicate which units or structures could host a geothermal reservoir and form the basis for subsequent conceptual and numerical models. The pH found range from 6 to 8,9 while the EC only the Kanvinvira has a higher than other 1453 μ S, Runingu is 800 μ S and Pemba is 673 μ S. The different directions of the joints, drop-offs, diachlases and veins attest to the existence of two phases of local deformation. The first phase produced syntectonic breaks in the first Kibaran regional folding, while the second phase produced breaks that accompanied the shearing of the East African rifting into the Tanganyikian trend.

The Uvira thermal springs are aligned along the same NNE-SSW direction (Runingu, Kanvinvira, Pemba). The healthy samples of the rocks from the various thermal springs show a rock with a greyish texture and a whitish color, dominated by silica (quartz), followed by feldspars and micas. The rock is thought to be granit, while on the other side there is a rock essentially composed of quartz that is thought to be quartzite and a schistose rock from Pemba spring.

Geophysical methods for those sites are recommended under the Congolese Geothermal Committee's guidelines for early exploration. As a result, Burundi, the Democratic Republic of Congo, and Rwanda will benefit from the target's geographic location at the intersection of the three ARGeo members.

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